

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Reassessing Return Migration Governance: Insights on Nigeria's Return Migration Infrastructures

Country Dossier (WP3)

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List of Abbreviations

AVRR	Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration
CMET	Case Management Team
COMPASS	Cooperation on Migration Partnerships to Achieve Sustainable Solutions
CSOnetMADE	Civil Society Network for Migration and Development
EU	European Union
FIIAP	Ibero-American Foundation for Administration and Public Policies
FME	Federal Ministry of Education
FMHAPR	Federal Ministry of Humanitarian Affairs and Poverty Reduction
FMLE	Federal Ministry of Labour and Employment
FMoH	Federal Ministry of Health
FMoJ	Federal Ministry of Justice
FMoWA	Federal Ministry of Women Affairs
GIZ	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit GmbH
ICMPD	International Centre for Migration Policy Development
IOM	International Organisation for Migration
IRARA	Integrated Return and Reintegration Assistance
MDAs	Ministries, Departments and Agencies
MET	Measurement and Evaluation Team
MFA	Ministry of Foreign Affairs
MRC	Migrant Resource Centre
MTC	Migrant Transit Centre
NACTAL	Network Against Child Trafficking, Abuse, and Labour
NAPTIP	National Agency for the Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons
NBS	National Bureau of Statistics
NCC	National Consultative Committee
NCFRMI	National Commission for Refugees, Migrants and Internally Displaced Persons
NDE	National Directorate of Employment
NEMA	National Emergency Management Agency
NIDCOM	Nigerians in Diaspora Commission
NIS	National Immigration Service
NMD	National Migration Dialogue
NOA	National Orientation Agency
NPC	National Population Commission
ONSA	Office of the National Security Adviser
PCI	Patriotic Citizens Initiative

RC	Reintegration Committee
RMI	Return Migration Infrastructures
SMEDAN	Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria
TWG	Technical Working Group
UNN	University of Nigeria Nsukka
WGRRR	Working Group on Return, Readmission and Reintegration
WOTCLEF	Women Trafficking and Child Labour Eradication Foundation

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Summary

Return migration has become a significant global policy priority, especially within Europe, as highlighted by the GAPS project under Horizon Europe (2023-2026). The project investigates the drivers of return policies and the disconnect between policy expectations and actual outcomes. By adopting a de-centering approach to migration governance, the project involves 17 partners from 12 countries across four continents, with a specific focus on Nigeria as part of Work Package 3 (WP3). This research explores the implementation of return migration governance through the concept of “Return Migration Infrastructures” and emphasises the relationships among various actors involved in return processes. The WP3 research aims to understand the complex interactions among state and non-state actors, their roles, practices, and the materials that shape return processes. This exploration reveals how these factors interact across multiple scales, creating nuanced realities on the ground. WP3 also investigates coercive elements, including assisted returns and forced removals, moving beyond simplistic distinctions between voluntary and forced returns. The research encompasses both EU and non-EU countries, including Germany, Greece, the Netherlands, Poland, Sweden, Georgia, Iraq, Morocco, Nigeria, Tunisia, and Turkey. Under the WP3, this particular work is a country dossier on Nigeria’s return migration infrastructure.

In Nigeria, the return migration infrastructure consists of a network of various government ministries, international organisations such as the International Organisation for Migration (IOM), the International Centre for Migration Policy Development (ICMPD), the German Agency for International Cooperation (GIZ), and the European Border and Coast Guard Agency (FRONTEX), alongside local civil society organisations. Together, these entities strive to ensure the safe and dignified return of Nigerian migrants. However, significant challenges persist, including poor coordination among ministries, insufficient community engagement, and a disconnect between policy formulation and practical execution. Conducted from June 2023 to June 2024, this research involved 15 in-depth interviews with stakeholders knowledgeable about return processes, as well as insights from return migrants. Notes from the Technical Working Group, Working Group on Return, Readmission and Reintegration and Reintegration Committee meetings as well as journal articles and online materials were also consulted.

The study outlines the detailed overview of Nigeria’s migration governance framework, which is structured across four hierarchical levels: National Consultative Committee, Technical Working Group, Sub-Thematic Committees and Reintegration Committee. It also examines the four distinctive stages of the return process: predeparture, arrival, reintegration, and monitoring and evaluation. Despite the existence of a comprehensive policy framework, issues such as corruption, limited grassroots involvement and low-capacity hinder effective implementation. These challenges reveal a power asymmetry in international cooperation that complicates governance and fosters dependency on international actors. The exclusion of local chiefs from the governance framework creates a problem, as their involvement is crucial for effective reintegration. The dynamics of international cooperation on return governance are characterised by hegemonic relationships between the EU and Nigeria. This power asymmetry is evident in trade and migration policies, with EU policies often dominating the discourse. Many Nigerian officials rely on European sponsorship for training and workshops, leading to a dependency that undermines local decision-making. Cooperation between Nigeria and the

EU has not proven efficient, with many returns characterised as coerced rather than voluntary, which undermine the dignity of returnees.

To enhance reintegration efforts, the National Commission for Refugees, Migrants, and Internally Displaced Persons must actively engage with CSOs, traditional chiefs and other stakeholders. Fostering a balanced partnership and equitable dialogues between Nigeria and the EU, strengthening capacity building, establishing robust networks among reintegration entities, and addressing root causes of migration, particularly poor governance, are essential. A coordinated approach among stakeholders is crucial for improving outcomes for returnees in Nigeria and strengthening the return migration infrastructure, ultimately fostering a more effective governance framework that supports the reintegration of returnees into society.

Keywords: assisted voluntary return and reintegration; coerced returns, deportation; European Union; forced returns; governance of return migration; Nigeria; North Africa; sub-Saharan Africa, return migration infrastructure

The GAPs Project

GAPs is a Horizon Europe project that aims to conduct a comprehensive multidisciplinary study of the drivers of return policies and the barriers to and enablers of international cooperation on return migration. The overall aim of the project is to examine the disconnects and discrepancies between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes by decentring the dominant, one-sided understanding of “return policymaking.” To this end, GAPs:

- examines the shortcomings of the EU’s return governance;
- analyses enablers of and barriers to international cooperation, and
- explores the perspectives of migrants themselves to understand their knowledge, aspirations and experiences with return policies.

GAPs combines its approach with three innovative concepts:

- A focus on return migration infrastructures, which allows the project to analyse governance gaps;
- An analysis of return migration diplomacy to understand how relations between EU member states and with third countries hinder cooperation on return; and
- A trajectory approach, which uses a socio-spatial and temporal lens to understand migrant agency.

GAPs is a three-year interdisciplinary research project (2023–2026), coordinated by Uppsala University and the Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies (BICC) with 17 partners in 12 countries on four continents. GAPs’ fieldwork has been conducted in 12 countries: Sweden, Nigeria, Germany, Morocco, the Netherlands, Afghanistan, Poland, Georgia, Turkey, Tunisia, Greece and Iraq.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background to the GAPs Project and WP3

Return migration has become a policy priority across the world, and especially in Europe. The GAPS project is a Horizon Europe project (2023-2026) that investigates the drivers of return policies, and the potential disconnects between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes on the ground. It follows a de-centering approach to migration governance and seeks to move beyond a Euro-centric understanding of return policymaking. The consortium consists of 17 partners in 12 countries across four different continents. This country dossier on Nigeria is part of Work Package (WP) 3 of the GAPS project. This work package aims to study how return migration governance is put in practice, through the concept of “Return Migration Infrastructures (RMIs)”, by focusing on the so-called “crucial meso-level” (Faist, 2010). Following the infrastructural turn in migration studies (e.g., Xiang & Lindquist, 2014), the aim is to understand the relations and interactions between a wide variety of actors and their roles, their practices (“doings”), as well as the materialities and technologies that together shape – i.e., facilitate, undermine or contest – the daily operation of returns. In doing so, it explores how the aforementioned work together on multiple scales and create messy realities on the ground through a range of practices (Koinova et al., 2021). Moreover, WP3 investigates an axis of coercion that includes three types of RMIs, namely the assisted returns, forced removals, and pushbacks, by going beyond simplistic binaries of voluntariness vs. forced returns (Sahin-Mencutek & Triandafyllidou, 2024). WP3 research was implemented in both EU and non-EU countries, particularly in Germany, Greece, the Netherlands, Poland, and Sweden, and Georgia, Iraq, Morocco, Nigeria, Tunisia, and Turkey. EU partner countries focus on RMIs returning people from the EU to either EU – in the case of Dublin – or non-EU while non-EU partners focus on RMIs receiving returnees from any location in the context of EU policies.

1.2 Introduction to Nigeria’s Case Study

For Nigeria, return migration infrastructure is a crucial component of migration governance framework of the country consisting of stakeholders that take an active role in the day-to-day activities that affect return migration outcomes in the country. It is a web of state and non-state actors including those from various government ministries, departments and agencies (MDAs) which are interacting with international organisations (IOs) like International Organisation for Migration (IOM), International Centre for Migration Policy Development (ICMPD), German Agency for International Cooperation (*Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit*) (GIZ) and recently European Border and Coast Guard Agency (FRONTEX) (GIZ, 2023; ICMPD, 2022a; IOM, 2019, 2023; IRARA, 2024). Next to these big institutions, local civil society organisations (CSOs) play an important role to ensure the safe, orderly, and dignified return of Nigerian migrants and their reintegration.

Through the collaborations and connections, the infrastructure provides comprehensive support for returnees, facilitating their reintegration into society by addressing returnees’ diverse needs and fostering effective coordination among stakeholders. These needs may be the challenges faced by returnees to reintegrate into Nigeria in destination or transit countries where undocumented Nigerian migrants must be identified and provided with documents to facilitate their return to Nigeria. However, the existing return migration infrastructure in Nigeria lack cohesive coordination among MDAs, IOs and CSOs and they may not adequately

engage local communities in the reintegration process. This leads to fragmented efforts and inefficiencies in the support as well as reinforcing social stigmatisation which exacerbate returnees' reintegration challenges (Uzomah et al., 2024). This report can be seen as a first response to the need for in-depth evaluations to assess the effectiveness of the current return migration infrastructure and its impact on the reintegration experiences of returnees to identify best practices and areas for improvement.

2. Methods

2.1 WP3's General Methodology

The WP3 research lasted from June 2023 to June 2024 and included two main tasks. First, creating an overview of RMIs in each partner country by producing flow maps through desk research. Desk research included the study of reports, policy briefs, informative leaflets, data reports, newsletters, websites, etc. on the implementation of returns, from involved actors and/or observers. Desk research and the flow maps produced are structured around i) the actors involved, ii) their doings, and iii) the materials and technologies used (Figure 1). Second, the WP3 research for Nigeria focused on the selection of assisted returns and forced removal RMI as a case study. The research started from telephone calls to the proposed interviewees, their offices and on the ground related to the everyday workings of assisted returns and forced removal. It included the implementation of 30 interviews in Nigeria with actors involved at the meso-level of the everyday operation of the return procedure, that may both facilitate and contest return operations including state and non-state actors. These interviews will be stored on the servers of Uppsala University.

2.2 Data Collection and Analysis Conditions in the Case Study

Despite our efforts to introduce the project, many participants initially expressed skepticism about granting interviews. This reluctance stemmed from defensiveness and a general distrust in the return and reintegration landscape in Nigeria. Stakeholders were often protective of their information, and there were rivalries both among and within government entities and implementing organisations. To address these challenges, we sought assistance of a local non-governmental organisation (NGO) with a history of collaboration with many of the interviewees, to help build trust. We employed a chain referral method, making an average of three calls to each participant before successfully scheduling an interview. All interviewees were provided with a consent form to participate. The interviewees included 15 individuals from both state and non-state actors, such as representatives from government agencies, civil society organisations, journalists, international organisations, and return migrants. Each interview was recorded in audio formats and subsequently transcribed into text. Additional information was gathered from notes and presentations from meetings of the Technical Working Group on Migration and Development, and the quarterly meetings of Working Group on Return, Readmission and Reintegration (WGRRR) thematic committee which were held in May 2023 and September 2023, respectively. Furthermore, data was collected from three Reintegration Committee meetings held in Enugu between January and November 2024, and stakeholder expert meetings for the GAPs project in Nigeria, held in November 2023 and February 2024. Finally, a focus group discussion was held with ten Nigerian migrants, aged between 25 and 40, who returned within the last ten years.

3. Context

3.1 Overview of RMI in Nigeria

Nigeria's Return Migration Infrastructure (RMI) is a complex network centered around three international airports, where returnees from the EU and North Africa are received by a multitude of stakeholders. Upon arrival, the Nigeria Immigration Service (NIS), the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA), and the Federal Ministry of Health (FMoH) provide initial screening and support, while local NGOs offer counselling, and states like Edo and Delta receive their indigenes. The RMI involves a wide array of actors, including numerous MDAs such as the National Commission for Refugees, Migrants and Internally Displaced Persons (NCFRMI), Federal Ministry of Humanitarian Affairs and Poverty Reduction (FMHAPR), Nigerians in Diasporas Commission (NIDCOM), Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MFA), National Bureau of Statistics (NBB) and National Agency for the Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons (NAPTIP), each playing specific roles in reintegration, from documentation and health screenings to economic empowerment and security coordination. The IOM, GIZ, and FRONTEX provide crucial financial and technical support, though FRONTEX's involvement has raised human rights concerns. CSOs and faith-based organisations (FBOs), contribute to reintegration and advocacy, while academic institutions are increasingly offering migration-related courses. The NCFRMI and IOM manage data, though inconsistencies persist. Other actors are the international partners like the European Union (EU), Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation (SDC), International Centre for Migration Policy Development (ICMPD), International Returns and Reintegration Assistance (IRARA), and Ibero-American Foundation for Administration and Public Policies (FIIAP). Despite their efforts, the RMI faces challenges with data management, coordination, and funding, hindering effective and sustainable reintegration. The roles and responsibilities of the actors involved in Nigeria's RMI to facilitate the return, readmission and reintegration (RRR) of migrants in Nigeria are captured in the flow map described below.

3.2 Brief Explanation of the Flow Map

This flow map we constructed which visually represents the complex network of Nigeria's RMI. It is based on the four stages of the return process in the country (Figure 1) and revolves within the migration governance framework of the country. The infrastructure is centered around three major international airports in Lagos, Abuja, Kano, where returnees from the EU and North Africa are processed upon arrival. The flow map highlights the various actors and roles involved in the return and reintegration of returnees, including the various government, ministries, departments and agencies (MDAs) like NIS, NEMA, and NAPTIP, NCFRMI, FMHAPR, and FMoH which provide initial documentation and health screenings. International partners like IOM, ICMPD, GIZ and FRONTEX contribute financial and technical support. Local NGOs play a crucial role by offering counseling and assistance, while states like Edo and Delta actively engage in receiving their indigene returnees. Furthermore, the flow map highlights the activities (doings) and materials including buildings, goods and support services and economic empowerment initiatives rendered to the returnees. Overall, the map serves to visualise the intricate processes, materials and actors involved in facilitating the return and reintegration of migrants, while also highlighting the challenges the RMI faces in terms of coordination and funding.

Figure 1: Return migration infrastructural flow map for Nigeria. Source: GIS Lab, Department of Geography and Environmental Sustainability, University of Nigeria Nsukka (2024)

3.3 Materials Used in the RMI

The returnees who are flown mainly from countries in the EU and North Africa are disembarked at three international airports in Nigeria namely, Murtala Mohamed International Airport Lagos, Nnamdi Azikiwe International Airport Abuja and Aminu Kano International Airport Kano (Figure 2). At the airport many MDAs and local NGOs are available to receive the returnees. The NIS screens the returnees for immigration related documents, the NEMA offers standby support such as water, food and ambulance. The migrants are taken to the Migrant Transit Centre (MTC) in Lagos where needs assessment is conducted, and referrals are made. In Kano, returnees are taken to a temporary holding facility provided by NEMA for a day or less, where they undergo screening before being instructed to return the following day for further processing. In Abuja, they are held in tents for one to two days for screening, and then similarly asked to return. The MTC exists only in Lagos at present, with proposed counterparts in Kano and Abuja. However, regardless of location, whether at the established MTC or the temporary holding facilities, the FMoH screens returnees for illnesses such as HIV/AIDS and tuberculosis. Local NGOs offer them counselling. Certain sub-national states, particularly Edo, Delta, and Kano, demonstrate a heightened focus on migration issues, actively retrieving their indigenes upon their return. This proactive approach is driven by the significant influence of migration within the local politics of these states, which serve as major sources or collective hubs for irregular migration. In contrast, migration matters tend to receive less attention in other Nigerian states. At the Migrant Transit Centre (MTC) and temporary holding facilities, computers are utilised to record returnee information and reintegration activities, a process managed by the NCFRMI in IOM. MDAs and CSOs also employ WhatsApp groups to communicate with returnees, for instance, to inform them about available skill or vocational training. The EU funds these digital tools, facilitated by the IOM, which raises concerns about the potential linkage of data collected by MDAs to an EU digital

platform, prompting questions regarding data management and sovereignty. This raises the possibility of a coerced element in the data collection process, where states feel pressured to use EU-funded systems, potentially compromising their control over sensitive information.

Figure 2: International airports of returnee disembarkment in Nigeria. Source: GIS Lab, Department of Geography and Environmental Sustainability, University of Nigeria Nsukka (2024)

The data is however fraught with inconsistencies as mentioned in an interview on the use of data in providing returnee support with a stakeholder from the International Centre for Women Empowerment and Child Development:

“Partially, I will say they (returnee support activities) are active because we have a lot of migrants who are coming to access them. But sometimes, you see that these opportunities are circulating with the same migrants. You don’t have different persons [migrants] coming for different empowerment programmes; they are the same persons. Where we need to put in focus is to work with IOM more to get new data. Many migrants who are currently returning not being featured into these opportunities. It is the same old database they have been using. If you tell some organisations to bring their database for this year, they do not have it; even if they do, the data is not accurate. We also need to put more light on where these people—I mean the migrants—are. They are unreachable, and they live very far. There is little or no funding for these actors to go that far, to reach out to these migrants. To meet up with the funders request, they [these organisations] bring on the old database.”

The quote highlights two key learning takeaways. Firstly, it reveals systemic inequities and data deficiencies within migrant empowerment programmes. The reliance on outdated data

and limited outreach leads to the exclusion of new arrivals, hindering effective reintegration and creating a gap between programme goals and implementation. Secondly, it underscores the impact of funders' influence and operational shortcomings. The prioritisation of funder compliance over genuine migrant needs, combined with poor data management and insufficient funding for field outreach, exerts negative impact on the monitoring of reintegration activities and the entire RRR programme.

3.4 Actors in the RMI

Actors involved in the RMI at the airport include officials from the host countries including Inland Enforcement Officers (IEOs) along with the representatives from the IOM, MFA and Federal Ministry of Justice (FMOJ). Local NGOs partnering with both the IEOs, and refugee networks abroad (like those from the European Reintegration Support Organisation network) travel to preach the benefit of AVR to migrants with failed asylum claims. These NGOs also serve as conduit, informing the NCFRMI about any impending removal of Nigerian migrant from abroad, as they get such information from their partners abroad. When the returnees arrive, the NGOs serving as the local partners, welcome the returnees at the airport and facilitate their immediate needs like accommodation and feeding, and continue to administer them with startup packs for some period of time, while updating their foreign partners on every step of the return and reintegration process.

Plate 1: GAPS researcher monitors the reception by the PCI director of a Netherlands-based returnee at the Nnamdi Azikiwe Airport, Abuja in December 2024. Courtesy: Ngozi Uzomah (2024).

Generally, the NCFRMI coordinates all airport activities, collaborates with the Nigeria Immigration Services (NIS), National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA), Federal Ministry of Labour and Employment (FMLE) to facilitate the process of return and reintegration (Figure 1). International organisations like IOM and GIZ are also available. The MDAs are instrumental in providing reintegration support, commencing from the returnees' arrival at the airport to their final reintegration into society. Below is a brief explanation of some of the actors involved in the return migration infrastructure in Nigeria:

National Commission for Refugees, Migrants, and Internally Displaced Persons (NCFRMI)

The National Commission for Refugees, Migrants, and Internally Displaced Persons (NCFRMI) holds the constitutional mandate to coordinate all return and migration activities within Nigeria (NCFRMI, n.d.; Nneli et al., 2022). Its primary responsibilities include providing strategic leadership and general coordination for RRR efforts, as well as convening and chairing the TWG and WGRRR meetings. Additionally, the NCFRMI documents returnees, establishes a national database to track their readmission and sustainable reintegration, and monitors and evaluates all services provided to returnees, including those for victims of trafficking and vulnerable persons.

Plate 2: Stakeholders brainstorm at the WGRRR meeting held at the Bristol Palace Hotel, Kano in September 2023. Courtesy: Ngozi Uzomah (2023)

To further decentralise migration governance and enhance its reach, the NCFRMI is currently establishing zonal offices across Nigeria's six geopolitical zones. These zonal coordinators play

a crucial role by chairing reintegration committees at the subnational level and coordinating the training of counsellors specialising in RRR. This decentralised structure, with its focus on subnational coordination and capacity building, is for the management of RRR at the grassroots level.

Nigeria Immigration Service (NIS) The NIS supports the NCFRMI in the documentation and proper identification of returnees and coordinates all security concerns and debriefings at the transportation and arrival stage at the airports. It facilitates dignified entrance into the country, prior to the reception that may be provided by the NCFRMI in collaboration with other partners and stakeholders. It also issues the Instrument of Safe Passage to the NCFRMI for Nigerian migrants who do not have document to return home and provides requisite regulation documents to returnees of other countries transiting through Nigeria.

Federal Ministry of Humanitarian Affairs and Poverty Reduction (FMHAPR)

As the federal ministry that supervises NCFRMI, the FMHAPR engages in the effective supervision of NCFRMI's RRR activities and facilitates linkage to social protection programmes. It liaises with relevant MDAs for the reintegration of returnees and supports NCFRMI in resource mobilisation for RRR.

Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MFA)

The MFA facilitates the signing of bilateral and multilateral agreements in collaboration with the FMoJ and inputs from NCFRMI. It provides predeparture counselling for presumed irregular Nigerian immigrants and failed asylum seekers on the available comprehensive services back in Nigeria so they may be able to make an informed decision to return home voluntarily.

Federal Ministry of Justice (FMoJ)

The FMoJ collaborates with Ministry of Foreign Affairs to ensure that Nigeria signs protective bilateral and multilateral agreements and ensures compliance of processes with signed agreements.

Federal Ministry of Labour and Employment (FMLE)

The FMLE develops labour and employment related migrant reintegration programmes and facilitates the linkages for returnees to existing and available employment and job opportunities such as National Electronic Labour Exchange. It establishes Job Centres and Migrant Resource Centres in the six geo-political zones of the country to help in the placement of returnees in available jobs.

Federal Ministry of Women Affairs (FMoWA)

The FMoWA facilitates family tracing and reintegration for unaccompanied and separated migrant children (USMC) in collaboration with NCFRMI and other relevant stakeholders upon arrival in Nigeria and the provision of alternative care services for USMC. It provides transit shelters upon arrival for children and transportation to destination after family tracing as well as linking female returnees to women empowerment programmes.

Federal Ministry of Health (FMoH)

The FMOH participates in the predeparture and evacuation stage for RRR in the provision of first aid and medical profiling. It provides health services including health screening, on infectious diseases such COVID 19, tuberculosis, HIV AIDS, etc for the returnees at the point of arrival through Port Health Services (a division of the Department of Public Health within the ministry). It also provides mental health assessment, psychosocial support first aid and appropriate referral for identified severe mental health cases at the point of arrival through the National Mental Health Programme. Furthermore, it facilitates linkages/access to hospitals and health facilities upon referral from the NCFRMI for medical treatment and health related issues.

Federal Ministry of Education (FME)

The FME liaises with subnational-level Ministries of Education and State Universal Basic Education for children especially USMC after obtaining records from the NCFRMI. It links with technical colleges to provide technical vocational education for returnees.

National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA)

The NEMA facilitates the evacuation of returnees and supports the provision of logistics arrangements (such as transportation, standby ambulance, luggage assistance, light setting, food, and water) to the returnees at the airport and hotel.

National Agency for the Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons (NAPTIP)

NAPTIP receives returnees who are Victims of Trafficking (VOTs) through referrals for further rehabilitation and reintegration assistance and supports the provision of profiling, counselling, psycho trauma healing therapy services for these set of vulnerable returnees. It also supports family tracing and reunification activities and provides rehabilitation and reintegration services to vulnerable set of returnees. Once returnees arrived in Nigeria and are taken to the Migrant Transit Centre, they are screened by NCFRMI and those who are suspected of being trafficked victims are referred to NAPTIP.

Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN)

After five days of activities and processes relating to the arrival stage, SMEDAN, a Nigerian agency under the Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment, in the post arrival stage collaborates with institutions like IOM to facilitate the socio-economic development of the returnees. By training returnees on how to start, build and run businesses successfully, it links them to the various training and empowerment centres and provides them with access to market and finance.

Office of the National Security Adviser (ONSA)

The ONSA among other functions in the RRR programme coordinates all security related activities of other security agencies in Nigeria from the arrival stage to the reintegration stage of the returning process.

National Orientation Agency (NOA)

The NOA provides orientation lecture to returnees during reintegration on patriotism and on existing government programmes and activities. It is involved in the overall monitoring and evaluation support in the implementation of the reintegration assistance. It also holds orientation session for service providers and staff of government agencies involved in the RRR

process on the need for humane treatment of the returnees especially victims of trafficking and vulnerable persons. Furthermore, it is involved in the monitoring and evaluation stage of the return process conducting filed monitoring visits to returnees' business sites and assesses impact of the reintegration support provided by NCFRMI and other partners.

National Population Commission (NPC)

The NPC establishes and maintains machinery for the continuous and universal registration of births, deaths, still births etc. and collects, collates, publishes and disseminates data on migration statistics including on RRR. It conducts research, monitors the national population policy and sets up a national population data bank including migration development with regards to RRR.

National Directorate of Employment (NDE)

The NDE provides training for the returnees on skills acquisition as a reintegration package and facilitates accessibility to starter packs and soft loans upon completion of training. It also provides business plan and skills development training for the returnees. It is sometimes difficult to distinguish the work NDE does and that of SMEDAN thereby creating problem of overlapping of schedule and coordination of activities.

Offices/Representatives of International Organisations and EU and Development Cooperation of European Countries

International development partners like the EU, SDC, IOM, GIZ, ICMPD, IRARA, FRONTEX FIIAP work hand-in-hand with the national authority in liaising with the host country's IEOs in the implementation of RRR whenever they are called upon to provide technical and or financial support needed for the sustainability of the programme. They also support RRR process in capacity building especially training and provision of reintegration programmes to returnees. These programmes offer a range of support services, including vocational training, financial assistance, and psychosocial counselling. For example, IOM is pivotal in managing the entire process of AVR, providing essential support for returnees. ICMPD offers policy advice and financial assistance to the Nigerian government regarding migration issues, including organising workshops and meetings to enhance understanding and cooperation. It is known for sponsoring migration workshops aimed at enhancing the capacity of stakeholders involved in the reintegration process. As Nigeria takes over the Chairmanship of the Rabat Process (2025-2026), ICMPD is supporting the Process by providing expertise, facilitating dialogue, and promoting sustainable return and reintegration strategies as part of comprehensive migration governance. FRONTEX collaborates with IRARA in the return and reintegration of Nigerian migrants. The role of FRONTEX has been controversial, with many viewing its activities as an infringement on human rights. Critics argue that its overzealous approach leads to violations of international laws, particularly in African contexts (Uzomah, 2024; Zhong & Carrapico, 2024). There are calls for the Nigerian government to take a firm stance against the EU's outsourcing of migration control to such organisation, with suggestions ranging from its abolition to necessary reforms to prioritise the protection of migrants. The GIZ provides technical cooperation and funding for various return activities in Nigeria, including stakeholder meetings and reintegration support in key cities like Abuja, Lagos, and Benin. GIZ has been successful in providing necessary support packages to returnees from Germany, facilitating smoother transitions and reducing the likelihood of conflict or dissatisfaction. These are usually for returnees from Germany, but GIZ has started

extending that to deportees from other countries, as shared in a stakeholder meeting. There are also critiques to extend the support to other underserved regions in Nigeria.

Civil Society Organisations (CSOs)

CSOs support the provision of reintegration assistance, in coordination and collaboration with relevant partners and monitor and evaluate the returnees' reintegration progress. They also assist in the monitoring of returnees' associations and engage in advocacy to improving RRR of returnee migrants. The CSOs are often more focused in their demands compared to government agencies, but they face challenges such as proliferation, funding limitations, and capacity building. Some CSOs are faith-based organisations (FBOs), which can make their training programmes less sustainable, particularly when they are run by individuals with limited resources. Under the umbrella of Society Forum (CSF), CSOs organise annual events to mobilise their members for a collective force. The 2024 event which was like a spillover from the 2024 National Migration Dialogue which was held the previous day, took place at Wells Carlton Hotel, Asokoro, Abuja, on December 10, 2024. Theme of the event is "Integrating Grassroot Perspective in the Global Compact for Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration Process: Overview of the Implementation of the GCM Obj. 21-Return, Readmission and Reintegration in Nigeria." Many entities working in issues of RRR were in attendance including those from the Rabat Process, GIZ, IOM, NCFRMI, ICMPD, IRARA, MDAs, EU delegation, academia, and returnees. There were several panel discussions. One was on the limited recognition of grassroots dynamics in reintegration policies and minimal involvement of non-state actors in bilateral and multilateral agreements. IRARA country representative was also given the opportunity to speak on the joint activities of IRARA with FRONTEX in the deportation of Nigerian migrants. At the end, it was learnt that IRARA's participation is based on the reality of removing irregularised migrants from the EU; if it does not, FRONTEX will find other means to do that. The highpoint of the event was when six returnees were invited to speak of their experiences in host countries and return and reintegration process. This event was sponsored by international organisations including IOM, GIZ, IRARA, and Nigerian-German Centre.

Academic Institutions

Nigerian academic institutions are increasingly focusing on return, readmission, and reintegration studies, shown by migration centre establishment and expanded courses. For example, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, offers postgraduate programmes in migration studies, including return migration (NAU, 2025). The National Open University of Nigeria, Abuja, in collaboration with the Munich Forum for Dialogue, is launching a two-semester programme on circular and return migration, targeting policymakers and CSOs to promote orderly returns. This trend is also seen in growing scholarly interest, especially at the Universities of Nigeria, Nsukka, and Elizade University in Ondo State. This academic surge is largely due to increased deportations from the EU and North Africa and shifting EU and U.S. return and deportation policies. Migration studies which is previously less common in Nigeria, is being popularised by EU's interest and increased focus on operational returns, particularly, in the country. This academic engagement is expected to strengthen Nigeria's RMI through evidence-based policies and enhanced data analysis.

3.5 Return Practices Within Nigeria's Migration Governance Framework (Doings)

Nigeria's migration governance framework establishes the structural organisation for coordinating migration across governmental levels and among various stakeholders. This system encompasses the principles, decision-making procedures, and processes by which organisations manage and direct migration dynamics, aiming to benefit all while prioritising the safety and well-being of migrants and Nigeria's socioeconomic development. Within this framework, a network of state and non-state actors collaborates to coordinate the return of Nigerian migrants, forming the country's Return Migration Infrastructure (RMI).

The framework operates on governing principles that emphasise integrity, fairness, transparency, and compliance with Nigerian laws, thereby promoting improved service delivery and accountability. It ensures the operationalisation of strategic documents, policies, and practices. Key policies include: the National Migration Policy (2015, currently under review), the National Policy on Health Workforce Migration (2023), the National Diaspora Policy (2021), the National Policy on Labour Migration (2014, reviewed 2020), the National Policy on Internally Displaced Persons (2012), the New Visa Policy (2020), and the Immigration Act of 2015 with its 2017 Regulation. These policies mandate that all actors, including employees, stakeholders, and partners, commit to good governance to facilitate orderly returns and sustainable reintegration.

Specifically, the 2019 Framework for Effective Assisted Voluntary Returns and Reintegration (AVRR) in Nigeria: Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) serves as a crucial guiding document for these policies and practices, particularly in implementing AVRR. The NCFRMI, in collaboration with relevant stakeholders and with technical support from the IOM, developed this SOP. Its core objectives include outlining a detailed procedural approach and timeline for AVRR implementation, ensuring effective coordination through clear communication pathways, and specifying the roles and operational limits of participating entities to secure the process's sustainability.

To ensure effective coordination, Nigeria's migration governance framework is structured across four hierarchical levels, defining the roles and responsibilities of actors in managing migration matters, including Return, Readmission, and Reintegration (RRR) processes, in line with international, regional, and national legal instruments as shown below:

1. The National Consultative Committee (NCC), also known as the Sector Policy Review Committee (SPRC) or Interministerial Committee, functions as the apex decision-making body for migration-related matters in Nigeria. This committee is comprised of ministers and heads of parastatals with migration-related mandates, and is co-chaired by the Attorney-General of the Federation/Minister of Justice and the Minister of the FMHAPR, who oversees the NCFRMI that provides secretariat support for NCC. The NCC's primary role is to make pivotal decisions on migration issues, including those related to RRR, based on detailed recommendations from the TWG. Given Nigeria's significant position in migration, particularly with the increasing emigration and deportation of its citizens, the NCC also plays a crucial lobbying role. Notably, it engages with the House Committee on Diaspora and the Senate Committee on Human Rights, as neither chamber of Nigeria's

national assembly has a dedicated committee for migration matters. Furthermore, individuals representing Nigeria in the signing of international agreements, Memorandums of Understanding (MOUs), and partnerships concerning returns and other migration matters are typically members of the NCC or are recommended by them for government approval.

2. **Technical Working Group (TWG):** This second-level coordinating body plays a crucial role in providing the NCC with well-researched, evidence-based recommendations. Comprising experts in the field, the TWG articulates facts and information on RRR. Led by NCFRMI, with strategically located zonal offices across Nigeria, the TWG facilitates decentralised processes and ensures that regional migration issues are effectively addressed. Regular quarterly meetings serve as platforms for addressing emerging migration challenges and receiving updates from five specialised thematic sub-committees.
3. **Thematic Sub-Committees:** Operating at the third level of coordination, these five specialised groups, including the Working Group on Return, Readmission, and Reintegration (WGRRR), are responsible for the operationalisation of strategic documents and the implementation of capacity-building initiatives. Other thematic groups include the Standing Committee on Diaspora Matters (led by NIDCOM); Labor Migration Working Group (led by FMLE); Border management Working Group (led by NIS); and the Migration Data Management Working Group (led by NPC). They report directly to the TWG, to ensure that all aspects of migration management including returns are comprehensively addressed.
4. **Reintegration Committee (RC):** Operating at the sub-national and local levels, this fourth-level committee coordinates return and reintegration activities at the grassroots level. It comprises state and non-state actors, including sub-national parastatals, CSOs, private sector entities, faith-based organisations, and other stakeholders acting at their respective institutional levels. Each participating entity has migration desk officers who are members of their corresponding working groups, as well as members of the TWG. This committee plays a vital role in data generation, case management, and monitoring and evaluation.

This governance framework, established in alignment with the NCFRMI Act 2022, outlines the governance measures, processes, and principles underpinning RRR efforts. It clarifies the roles of the NCFRMI board, management, NCC, TWG, and development partners to promote collaboration and communication. However, the framework is significantly influenced by the EU and its member states, who among others sponsor quarterly meetings, policy development, and reviews, facilitated through organisations like IOM, ICMPD, and GIZ.

Plate 3: Nigeria GAPs team joins stakeholders at the RC meeting held at the Federal Secretariat Enugu, Nigeria in 2024. Courtesy: Ngozi Uzomah (2024).

3.6 National Migration Dialogue

The NCFRMI convenes the annual National Migration Dialogue (NMD), a vital platform institutionalised in 2014 to commemorate the United Nations' International Migrants Day. This multi-stakeholder forum brings together government agencies, international organisations, civil society groups, academics, and migrants themselves to engage in critical discussions on migration's complex challenges and opportunities within the Nigerian context. Each NMD is strategically designed around a theme relevant to the prevailing migration landscape.

In 2021, the NMD aligned with the global theme of International Migrants' Day, "Mobility and People on the move." The event featured dedicated sessions, including Civil Society Day (CSD), which facilitated in-depth discussions on strategies for ensuring the sustainability of migration programs for national development. The Common Space sessions provided a platform for stakeholders to formulate actionable and sustainable recommendations for enhancing national migration governance. Key outcomes of the 2021 NMD included advocating for improved consular activities to build trust with destination countries and protect the rights of Nigerian nationals abroad, as well as emphasising the need for sustainable reintegration programmes to prevent irregular re-migration. Participants also highlighted the importance of collaborative efforts between the government, CSOs, and academia in reviewing and

improving migration policies, and suggested a strategic shift towards prioritising labour migration over return and reintegration, aligning with national development goals.

The 2023 NMD, themed “Leveraging on youth migration (Japa Movement) for National Development,” directly addressed the pressing issue of youth emigration, reflecting the growing concerns surrounding the “Japa” phenomenon (desperate emigration of mainly youth). The event’s significance was underscored by the high-level participation of the IOM Chief of Mission in Nigeria, Laurent M. L. De Boeck, and the Minister of Humanitarian Affairs and Poverty Alleviation, Dr. Betta C. Edu, demonstrating the government’s commitment to addressing this critical issue.

The 2024 National Migration Dialogue, themed, “Beyond Borders: Celebrating Migrants’ Legacy, Protecting their Rights” which was held on December 9, 2024 spotlighted pressing issues like RRR. The dialogue delved deep into how Nigeria can better reintegrate returned migrants into society, addressing practical solutions and policy frameworks, directly aligning with the goal of crafting sustainable, rights-based approaches to reintegration. The issue of desperate emigration was also tackled, underscoring the urgent need to address the systemic factors driving outward migration. Thus, stakeholders are now better equipped to advocate for policies that address these root causes while easing the burden on return migration systems.

Attending the 2024 NMD was Vice President Kashim Shettima who made a powerful call for countries and stakeholders to prioritise the dignity and rights of migrants, regardless of their status, emphasising the fundamental principles of human rights and respect. The dialogue’s lineup of dignitaries and stakeholders included Speaker of the House of Representatives Rt. Hon. Tajudeen Abbas, Deputy Speaker Hon. Benjamin Kalu, Federal Commissioner for Refugees, Migrants, and Internally Displaced Persons Hon. Tijjany Ahmed, Chairman of the Nigerians in Diaspora Commission Hon. Abike Dabiri-Erewa, Interim Country Chief of IOM Paola Pace, and representatives from the German and U.S. embassies, the European Union delegation, the ICMPD, CSOs, academics, and government agencies. This high-level attendance underscores the growing significance of migration, particularly in light of the increasing number of deported Nigerian migrants.

As Nigeria grapples with the multifaceted complexities of migration, the 2024 National Migration Dialogue marks a pivotal moment in shaping a more humane and effective migration governance framework, one that prioritises the dignity and rights of all migrants, returnees, and their communities. For many stakeholders, this event represents a significant springboard to deepen its impact, influence policies, and advocate for a migration system that works for everyone.

A key takeaway from NMD in general is that it stands as a vital, multi-stakeholder platform for addressing Nigeria’s evolving migration challenges, evidenced by its consistent focus on timely themes like youth emigration and reintegration, highlighting the importance of collaborative dialogue in shaping national policies. Additionally, despite the emphasis on labour migration, there is gradual shift focusing on return migration. Furthermore, the NMD underscores that effective migration governance in Nigeria requires a comprehensive approach, prioritising the protection of nationals abroad, sustainable reintegration, and addressing the root causes of irregular migration, emphasising the need for holistic, rights-

based solutions. However, a notable absence within the NMD is the limited participation of traditional and community leaders, despite the presence of some religious leaders.

3.7 Migrant Transit Centre and Migrant Resource Centre

Migrant Transit Centre (MTC) serve as temporary residence for returnees and displaced persons in Nigeria. Funded by the EU and implemented by IOM, this center provides immediate assistance to returnees for approximately five days upon their arrival, before they proceed home or are referred to relevant agencies. Lagos hosts a transit center capable of accommodating up to 400 people, which became fully operational in May 2022 and has since welcomed over 1,000 returnees. A second one is being proposed in Kano thereby expanding Nigeria's RMI.

Complementing these transit centers are Migration Resource Centres (MRC), which function as information hubs and job centers. These centers offer potential and returning migrants access to relevant migration information and other services. Two MRCs have been established by the Federal Ministry of Labour in Lagos and Abuja, within an EU-funded project implemented by IOM. In Abuja, Germany's development minister inaugurated the center designed to support Nigerians returning from Germany. Additionally, a third center is located in Benin City. This project aims to improve labor migration management in Nigeria, including providing information for returnees. Furthermore, four job centers in Asaba, Kaduna, Bauchi, and Awka States are being proposed under the same project. IOM has provided training to staff on the operation of these centers. However, these centres are inadequate to address the needs of returnees as they are not sufficiently equipped with materials and viable information.

4. Stages of Return Process in Nigeria

In Nigeria, the return process is structured into four distinct stages: pre-departure, arrival, reintegration, and monitoring and evaluation. Multiple actors are involved in managing returns and administering and operationalising returnee support programme.

4.1 Predeparture Stage

This stage constitutes of counselling and administrative activities to prepare the migrants for their return to the origin country. It involves addressing identity issues and procuring travel documents. Some returnees may provide incorrect identities when seeking asylum abroad, which complicates their reintegration upon return. Identifying their correct identities at home might be challenging but is generally considered to be manageable. When return assistance is initiated, it often leads to the revelation of their true identities, allowing for the rectification of any discrepancies in their documentation. This process is crucial for ensuring that returnees can access the support and services available to them upon their return.

The process for obtaining a travel certificate or an Instrument of Safe Passage for undocumented migrants preparing to return is notably complex and fraught with difficulties. One of the main barriers is the inadequacy of civil registration in Nigeria, which hampers the ability to properly identify returnees. Many individuals lack essential identification documents, such as a National Identification Number or a Bank Verification Number, which complicates the issuance of identity cards necessary for their return in Nigeria missions

abroad. Moreover, many Nigerian migrants are apprehensive approaching Nigeria embassies abroad because rather than supporting them, embassy staff collaborate with host country officials to facilitate their deportation.

A recent troubling incident involved approximately 100 Nigerians without passports being transited through Addis Ababa airport, raising concerns about the lack of proper documentation for returnees from various regions, particularly the Middle East. This highlights the differences between intra- African and Europe-based returns.

When migrants return home, they get a diverse range of training opportunities, encompassing hard skills (technical expertise), soft skills (interpersonal abilities), and entrepreneurship skills. Returnees who face mental health challenges are offered counselling services to support their reintegration process. However, several challenges hinder the effectiveness of these skill acquisition programmes. One significant issue is the potential mismatch between the skills acquired and the needs of the labour market in the returnees' home countries. For instance, skills that are in demand in the host countries may not translate effectively into job opportunities back in Nigeria. Furthermore, some returnees may choose training programmes that do not align with their personal interests or career aspirations. Also, when selecting a particular skill acquisition programme, returnees often consider the social benefits associated with the training, as well as the proximity of the training centre to their residence.

4.2 Arrival Stage

After the initially identification and verification, returnees land at airports. The returnees are administratively classified into two main categories: voluntary returnees and deportees. Voluntary returnees are individuals who choose to return to their home country on their own accord, while deportees are those forcibly returned, often based on referrals from various authorities. Upon arrival, both categories of returnees are received at the airport by government officials and non-governmental organisations (NGOs), which then conduct a profiling process. The MDAs play a significant role in this identification process, ensuring that returnees are properly documented and assessed. After the initial profiling, returnees are referred to the International Organisation for Migration (IOM) for further assistance, including medical evaluations and in-kind financial support. This process aims to ensure that returnees receive necessary care and resources to facilitate their reintegration into society.

Next to these formal administrative divides of voluntary vs. forced returns, there are other differentiations that matter significantly in our understanding of return processes to Nigeria. For instance, we notice a difference based on stigma and shame. Some of the returnees who are ashamed of their return will travel by themselves to meet family and friends and disappear without being noticed. Those who are not ashamed and those who even though ashamed, have no other option will allow themselves to be driven by bus, taxi accompanied by government agencies, CSOs and IOM officials to hotel, shelter or the Migration Transit Centre in Ikeja where they are housed for maximum of two weeks for needs assessment and profiling. The centre has rooms which are compartmentalised for men and women. At the centre, the Lagos State Emergency Management Agency, NCFRM, IOM, NAPTIP, FMOH are involved to screen and making referrals for the returnees. IOM is always at the background to provide technical and financial support. Unaccompanied migrant children and the disabled are referred to the FMOWA Those of them who are found to be trafficked are referred to NAPTIP which provide

psychological support to them. The returns who need health care because of sickness are referred to the FMoH. Once returnees who are taken to the Migrant Transit Centre are screened by NCFRMI and NIS, those who have health issues are referred to the FMoH which then may recommend them to hospitals or CSOs. There is usually no connection between the activities of health agencies of returning countries and that of Nigeria. Even when information about health of a returnee is passed to Nigerian authorities, they are vague making it difficult for follow up. Reports of deaths and abusive deportations of sick and unfit migrants (Uzomah, 2025) prompted CSOs to contest these abusive returns in early 2025, as evidenced by information on the TWG online platform, of which I am a member (Text box A)

Textbox A – Abuses and Demand for Urgent Reform in Nigerian Deportations

On February 6, 2025, in Abuja, a coalition of prominent civil society organisations—the Civil Society Network for Migration and Development (CSOnetMADE) and the Network Against Child Trafficking, Abuse, and Labour (NACTAL)—held a pivotal press conference, not merely to report, but to sound an alarm. They aimed to expose the deepening crisis of human rights violations inflicted upon Nigerian deportees, a crisis that stains the integrity of both Nigerian and European migration practices. The organisations presented compelling, deeply disturbing evidence of systemic abuse, with the case of Bright Obasuyi serving as a stark and horrifying illustration of the brutality faced by returning migrants.

Bright Obasuyi, who arrived in Lagos on January 22, 2025, in a critical, unconscious state, endured a systematic campaign of dehumanisation at the hands of German authorities. Dr. Emeka Obiezu of CSOnetMADE meticulously detailed the forced administration of medication, violent physical assault, and the use of restraints, all while Obasuyi suffered from documented medical conditions such as schizophrenia and epilepsy. This was not an isolated incident but a symptom of a larger, deeply troubling pattern.

The CSOs condemned the alarming lack of effective consular intervention from Nigerian officials. Obasuyi's own testimony revealed that Nigerian representatives prioritised the verification of his citizenship for deportation, effectively acting as facilitators rather than protectors of his rights. This apparent complicity implicates systemic failures within Nigerian migration governance and necessitates immediate, thorough reform. The organisations demanded an immediate, independent, and transparent investigation into these egregious abuses, insisting that those responsible, both in Germany and potentially within Nigerian agencies, be held accountable. They further demanded a radical overhaul of the reception conditions for deportees arriving in Nigeria, calling for the provision of comprehensive medical, psychological, and legal support to address the severe trauma inflicted upon them.

Furthermore, the CSOs urgently called for a comprehensive review and revision of Nigeria's Standard Operating Procedures for return, readmission, and reintegration. These procedures, they argued, must be aligned with international human rights standards, incorporating robust mechanisms for monitoring and accountability to prevent future abuses. They implored the Nigerian government to engage in robust and urgent diplomatic negotiations with German authorities and other relevant European nations, demanding guarantees that all future deportations are conducted with humane practices, respecting the fundamental rights of all individuals.

Osita Osemene of PCI and NACTAL emphasised the critical lack of coordinated government support for deportees, who are often left abandoned at airports without essential documentation, financial assistance, or adequate reintegration programmes. This abandonment, he argued, constitutes a further violation of their rights and exacerbates the trauma they have already endured. The CSOs reiterated their unwavering commitment to advocating for fundamental policy reforms that safeguard the dignity and rights of Nigerian migrants. They demanded immediate, decisive, and transparent action from the Nigerian government [as well as that of Germany and others] to prevent further human rights violations, ensure that justice is served for those affected, and restore faith and commitment to protecting Nigerian migrants.

This press conference was not merely a call for action; it was a demand for a fundamental shift in perspective, a recognition that the treatment of Nigerian migrants and returnees reflects the very soul of a commitment to human dignity.

4.3 Reintegration Stage

Then follows the reintegration stage. At this stage, family tracing is done and those who are lucky are reunified with their family members. The returnees at the stage receive training and start up packs from organisations and initiatives like IOM, GIZ, and Cooperation on Migration Partnerships to Achieve Sustainable Solutions (COMPASS) through local NGOs such as Patriotic Citizens Initiative (PCI), Women Trafficking and Child Labour Eradication Foundation (WOTCLEF), and Web of Hearts which can keep the returnees up to six months in their shelter. The returnees also receive psychosocial support. There is continuous counselling throughout the stages to make sure that returnees are reinserting into the society. SEDAN trains the returnees in skill acquisition and capacity building on business, thereafter they are given money to start their own. Some of them are also trained in hair salon, welding and fishery business. Faith-based organisations also contribute to returnee support. Pastors and priests from various churches organise activities to bring returnees together. While some returnees are reluctant to participate, believing these organisations lack the financial resources to meet their needs, others, driven by their religious faith, find the church's involvement crucial for their reintegration and seek spiritual succor. Similarly, communities, including friends and families, play a vital role in reintegration, offering both psychological and economic support. However, they can also be a source of societal stigma, as some communities perceive returnees as failures.

Moreover, stakeholders reported a mismatch between acquired skills and local opportunities, hindering sustainable reintegration. Beyond improving reintegration programs, some argue that the root causes of desperate migration, namely bad governance, must be addressed to prevent the factors that initially compelled individuals to leave. As one stakeholder stated in an interview:

“The principle of good governance is very important to development, once there is good governance the issue of migration which is however a human right will be reduce. Because the number at which people are moving is based on bad government and people are looking for greener pastures. We also need to get to know and enlighten people that the grass is actually not so green on the other side, and this is a false and

there should be an improve an ecosystem of information sharing and people are educated on the danger of irregular migration because if one has the right documents then there won't be any form of irregular migration. The receiving country must be abided by international obligation of the various treaties and the policies and there should not be a lacuna from the sending country and the receiving country. They should also look inward and respect all the obligation in the space”.

4.4 Monitoring and Evaluation Stage

During the monitoring and evaluation stage, the reintegration activities are implemented by the case management team (CMET). These include identifying the needs of the returnees through case management activities and providing reintegration support items and trainings to the returnees. Subsequently, the monitoring and evaluation team (MET) then assesses the effectiveness of the reintegration activities. They do this by measuring the quality of the support received by the returnees and their impact on their lives and reports to the WGRRR. The CMET and MET work on directly with the returnees and their progress and report to the Reintegration Committee which then feed the WGRRR on their progress. These activities are done by NGOs which happen mainly in Benin, Lagos, Kano and Abuja. The international organisations including, IOM, GIZ and ICMPD are involved in the implementation as well as capacity building while FRONTEX is involve in giving capacity to NIS on border management. In recent time, FRONTEX is collaborating with IRARA in the return of Nigerian migrants and their and reintegration in the country (Uzomah & Marino, 2024).

5. Relations, Synergies and Frictions

The relations, synergies and frictions among the actors in Nigeria's RMI is analysed below. It covers two the policy shortcomings and the challenges in cooperation on returns.

5.1 Policy Shortcomings

Nigeria has established a comprehensive policy framework for the sustainable reintegration of returnees, including the National Migration Policy of 2015, the Standard Operating Procedure on Return, Readmission, and Reintegration, and the Action Plan Policy Document on Return and Reintegration. While these documents outline a clear strategy for reintegration, significant challenges remain in their implementation.

A critical question is the extent to which these policies are being effectively implemented. There is often a disconnect between policy formulation and practical execution, which hampers the success of reintegration initiatives. There are numerous actors in Nigeria's reintegration sector with the capacity to implement programmes effectively. However, the lack of a harmonised approach across different organisations poses challenges. A unified strategy would enhance collaboration and improve outcomes for returnees.

Despite the elaborate RMI structure in the country, the governance framework is not effective. It is fraught by issues such as corruption, low capacity in terms of shortage of qualified personnel, and poor coordination among MDAs, CSOs and IOs which hinder the effectiveness of the RRR. The power imbalance between European and Nigerian actors creates an avenue for corruption which remains a significant barrier, with funds intended for return programmes

often misappropriate and misapplied, as shared by stakeholders. Corruption can undermine migrant-supporting organisations and migration governance (Schreier, 2024). This necessitates a focus on managing existing resources effectively to mitigate corruption's impact. There is a lack of coordination and often inadequate collaboration between Nigerian government agencies and international partners, leading to inefficiencies in the return process. There are noticeable lapses in the coordination between Nigerian authorities and international partners. Sometimes, these partnerships serve the interests of foreign entities rather than benefiting Nigeria. Many government agencies face zero budgets, limiting their capacity to implement effective return programmes and initiatives. There is a pressing need to ensure the safe, orderly, and dignified arrival of returnees, which is often compromised by the current inefficiencies. Many private organisations lack the necessary capacity to assist effectively, while public organisations are often plagued by corruption, underscoring the urgent need for public sector reform. Some of these challenges are captured in a speech by a participant at the stakeholders' expert panel conducted in Abuja in November 2023:

“Overall, reintegration support programmes in Nigeria show signs of success, although they are not without challenges. Key issues include inadequate funding for various programmes and a shortage of qualified personnel in the reintegration sector. To ensure the sustainability of these initiatives, it is crucial for the Nigerian government to commit budgetary resources to support reintegration activities effectively. Returnees do not have a clear understanding of what they are entitled to upon their return. Sometimes, their hopes and expectations are too high, only to be dashed at the end. Accurate information about the support available to them are not provided sufficiently thereby creating false hopes. This leaves them unprepared for the challenges they may face upon reintegration”

Creating of higher expectations among returning migrants and not meeting them in Nigeria is a major challenge hindering reintegration of the returnees. Furthermore, returnees frequently express dissatisfaction with their experiences, sometimes wishing to return to the countries from which they were expelled. For instance, reports from interactions between Nigerian CSOs and European partners reveal that returnees often reach out to complain about their lack of opportunities upon returning home. An interview with a local NGO, Humanitarian Care for Displaced Persons, reveals:

“Sometimes when the people are not properly reintegrated, they gather some money even through whatever programme they have gotten skills from and migrate back to the country [they were returned from]. They prefer these so-called countries they have been brought back from. So, most times when you return people involuntarily you tend to experience things like this [remigration tendencies]. I have had people who have been returned in the past through Senegal; so many of them want to get back to Europe through the same route...”

This highlights the urgent need for better pre-departure education and realistic expectations to prevent disillusionment. There are shelter issues. Many NGOs may overcommit to providing shelter for returnees, leading to situations where they cannot accommodate new arrivals once the initial commitments are fulfilled.

Economic reintegration of the returnees is also a major issue. All these create a bottleneck in the reintegration process as captured in a stakeholders' expert panel by a participant:

“Their [Returnees'] resilience and coping strategies are poor because many of them do not have the wherewithal. The ability of returnees to cope with their new circumstances significantly depends on their individual situations. Psychosocial support and counselling are vital components in helping returnees build resilience. Such support enables them to confront the realities of their post-return lives and fosters a sense of stability. Returnees often employ various coping strategies to navigate their new circumstances. Psychosocial support plays a critical role in this process, guiding returnees to accept their realities and adapt accordingly. Additionally, there is lack of economic support that can greatly enhance their ability to manage day-to-day challenges and contribute to their overall well-being”.

Also, the composition of the NCC raises concerns regarding its effective leadership. The appointment of Federal Ministry of Justice as the chair appears incongruous with the specialised nature of migration governance. Given the Ministry's broader portfolio encompassing issues beyond migration, its capacity to provide focused and informed leadership to the NCC is questionable. Consequently, the NCC has reportedly remained inactive since the establishment of Nigeria's migration governance framework. To enhance the NCC's operational efficacy, consideration should be given to appointing a chairperson from a ministry with a more direct and primary mandate related to migration. Furthermore, reports from stakeholders' meetings indicate a concerning trend of excluding individuals who express critical perspectives from the TWG and the sub-thematic groups, potentially stifling open dialogue and diverse viewpoints within this key operational body.

Furthermore, participatory observation by the authors revealed that local IOM staff who train reintegration committee members, in some cases, are merely showcasing they are providing, but not actually to providing them with capacity. In other words, the approach seems more about optics and performativity than actually impacting knowledge. Consequently, they do not probe if the trainees are following or not. They also do not share all the materials for the training which buttress their intention not to actually train the trainees but make a show of it. They haphazardly ask some staff members of MDAs to provide list of participants for the training without recourse to who need what and whether the trainees including those from CSOs are into return and reintegration or in different sectors. Some CSOs are fraudulent, they establish several NGOs to access funds simultaneously rather than to help returnees. The more NGOs each individual has, the more funding they receive for reintegrating returnees.

At the Reintegration Committee level, some vendors have been accused of being incompetent. Vendors are typically local businesses, service providers, NGOs, and financial service providers that IOM contracts with to deliver various forms of reintegration assistance. However, some CSOs have accused local IOM staff of using vendors who are usually their family members and friends and who may not be competent in what they do. The case managers are forced to recommend these vendors that are linked to local IOM staff otherwise the request of the returnees will not be approved. The implication is that the recommended items stand a high risk of being fake or compromised. A CSO member stated:

“I was forced to recommend a particular shop to a lady returnee who needed sowing machine after she completed her vocational training. I recommended the shop at Ring Road to her. When she got to the shop, she called me to complain that she does not like the sowing machines in the shop. When I enquired to know the reason, she said they are not strong machines. We had no option at that moment, and she yielded to collecting the machine. Can you believe that after three months, the lady called to complain that the machine has spoiled? She used the money she made for two months to repair the machine. The machine spoiled again after another two months, and now the machine is lying in the shop without being put into use. Is that not a waste?”

CSOs and returnees complained of forcing returnees to receive generator sets and tailoring materials from designated vendors. Some journalists have face blacklisting for call out on choosing from designated vendors. It was also discovered that at the case management level, the main needs of the returnees are not considered. Some returnees are averse to trading, business and commercial activities, but are compelled into buying and selling. A returnee complained:

“They are forcing me to train with SMEDAN. Brother, that is not my call. I do not like buying and selling because I know I will fail woefully. I prefer to go to school. If they can help me to take JAMB (entrance exam into Nigeria Universities) and sponsor my university education, then I will be okay. I like education, not buying and selling and distribution of goods.”

There are also grievances from some MDAs that local IOM staff are giving referrals to NGOs without informing the NCFRMI, which increases the chaotic nature of the reintegration support system in the country. NCFRMI states that it is not proper to by-pass them and work with local NGOs because they have the constitutional mandate to monitor and make sure that the returnees are reintegrated. Also, the IOM does not know the exact thematic areas of the NGOs and when they give them support for reintegration, it poses a challenge for NCFRMI to coordinate in such circumstance. Some personnel from NCFRMI just do the referrals without consulting other regions of the country (geopolitical zones). Instead of referring the returnees to where they are supposed to be reintegrated, they just stay in big cities to refer the returnees to the NGOs belonging to their friends and cronies, highlighting highly centralised nature of reintegration activities. The evident sycophancy displayed by officials of MDAs toward international organisations such as IOM, ICMPD, and GIZ during meeting and events raises serious concerns. Instead of conducting critical evaluations of these organisations' activities within Nigeria, officials praise them for funding meetings, including travel, accommodation, and daily subsistence allowances. This compromises their position and impedes their capacity to effectively question the organisations' operations, indicating that Nigerian government officials may prioritise short-term economic benefits over national sovereignty and the protection of migrants' rights. Though the NCFRMI has the constitutional mandate to coordinate reintegration efforts in Nigeria, there is a shared perception that it is not effectively fulfilling this role. When returnees do not receive adequate support from NCFRMI upon return, some CSOs often step in to fill the gaps. When events are taken place, CSOs and other MDAs claim that these events are unnecessarily dominated by NCFRMI. Some ask “How can one agency [NCFRMI] make video on migration only about itself, and forgets to add that of

others? They do not want the work of others to be prominent like theirs. They always overshadow others”.

Moreover, both the CSOs and some MDAs grumbled about the disturbing manner in which FRONTEX is collaborating with IRARA to return Nigerian migrants who are sick, drugged, or unfit for return thereby jeopardising returnees’ reintegration and abusing the return and reintegration initiative. This is flawed as some migrants who are returned look sick and frail. Many of them have been forced to return rather than voluntarily returned (Uzomah & Marino, 2024). A group of CSO members stated that a 6-year autistic baby deported with her mother is always aggressive and keep cutting everything in the house including electric wires which may endanger his life and that of others. The mother keeps on shouting to him. They asked, “How could authority deport that kind of people?” This is not an isolated case. Also, a family of five, caught our attention during fieldwork.

Textbox B: Case Study of a Deported Family

During fieldwork in Nigeria, our team encountered a family of five – a single mother and her four children – forcibly deported from Germany, revealing the profound and multifaceted trauma inflicted by such actions and the subsequent challenges of reintegration. The children, particularly the youngest, who was 12 at the time of deportation and is now 13, and the 14-year-old sister, exhibited severe trauma symptoms, including selective mutism, persistent fear, anxiety, and withdrawal. These symptoms were compounded by the deeply humiliating and terrifying experience of being removed from their school and handcuffed, a memory that continued to haunt them.

Victoria, the eldest daughter (now 18, but 17 at the time of deportation), who had lived in Germany since the age of 9 and had completed primary school, middle school, and secondary school, and was scheduled to begin film school, described her brother's severe depression and her own struggle to find employment in Nigeria. “From one day to the next, my life turned upside down,” she recounted. “We had to leave the country [Germany] where my siblings and I would have had a future. The country we grew up, have friends, relatives and acquaintances.” She expressed that Germany is where she calls home. “Our hearts still beat in Germany.” and continued to express that, “My greatest heart’s desire is to return to Germany, even if I may have to leave my entire family behind in Nigeria, because in Germany I have a perspective that I will never have here.” She attributed her difficulty finding work to her Euro-English accent, fearing it would expose their deportation history and lead to further stigmatisation and social isolation. “I can't put life here in Nigeria into words,” she shared, “When we first returned, we lived in Benin, and because of stigma, we relocated here in Abuja. Both in Benin and Abuja, we find everything foreign –the culture, the language, the attitude, the heat, the hygienic conditions, the customs, everything you can think of.” Their mother appeared depressed and agitated, with reports of aggressive and confrontational behaviour leading to eviction from a previous residence in another part of Abuja.

The family’s financial situation was dire, exacerbated by the cessation of support from local organisations. Adding to their distress was the German authorities’ demand for repayment of deportation costs as a condition for the Victoria’s return for schooling, a seemingly

impossible requirement. This potential return also raised serious concerns about procedural irregularities in the initial deportation, hinting at potential violations of their rights.

Attempts to facilitate their return and provide support by their lawyer in Germany and a transnational activist organisation, Refugee4Refugee, were ultimately unsuccessful. The lawyer cited Victoria's escalating financial demands and her decision to pursue an alternative, undisclosed route to Europe, which invalidated the agreed-upon support. When the GAPs team contacted experts in Germany, they acknowledged the severely limited support available for such cases, citing bureaucratic challenges and Victoria's stated desire for remigration rather than reintegration in Nigeria. They expressed uncertainty about the effectiveness of connecting the family with SOLOWODI, an NGO for migrant and refugee women in distress in Germany, given Victoria's strong desire to return.

This case study illuminates the devastating impact of forced deportation, revealing the complex reintegration challenges and severe limitations of support systems in both Germany and Nigeria. The desperation expressed by Victoria to remigrate underscores the urgent need for humane, rights-based migration policies. Several key issues emerge from this case. Firstly, the deported four children, with their high fluency in German (which is effectively their mother tongue), possess strong qualifications for a residence permit under German law. Being under 21 years old and having legally attended school in Germany for over four years, they meet the criteria for being considered "well-integrated" (European Council on Refugees and Exiles, 2025). Secondly, the demand by German authorities for a refund of the deportation costs, coupled with the potential return of Victoria and her brother, raises serious concerns about procedural irregularities in their initial deportation. This hints at potential violations of their rights during the deportation process.

Upon their return to Nigeria, the family faces significant reintegration challenges, mirroring those identified by Wapmuk (2019): abandonment, lack of sustainable employment, and stigmatisation as hindrances of reinsertion of returnees into Nigeria's society. Victoria's fear, stemming from her Euro-English accent, leads to social isolation, economic hardship, and psychological trauma, severely hampering family reintegration. The absence of sustainable employment opportunities directly exacerbates their financial and emotional distress. Furthermore, the observed 'aggressiveness' of their mother may be a manifestation of paradoxical self-stigma, a coping mechanism developed to contest the marginalisation, discrimination, and profound sense of abandonment they experienced.

The profound psychological and economic trauma endured by this family serves as a stark reminder of the complex interplay of legal, social, and emotional factors inherent in forced return. The desperation for remigration also raises critical ethical questions about the responsibilities of host countries post-deportation, particularly when potential procedural irregularities may have contributed to their removal. This case underscores the imperative for a just and compassionate approach to migration management that extends beyond the act of deportation and considers the long-term well-being and rights of returnees.

Despite the involvement of support organisations, Victoria and her family have suffered greatly, and the same is with other return migrants in Nigeria who continue to experience

harsh conditions upon return. Allegations during stakeholders meetings suggest that certain support organisations provided only short-term accommodation, limited to three days, for returnees under their purview, after which they were reportedly evicted. Furthermore, these returnees have alleged that they were subjected to threats of police intervention by representatives of these organisations. Notably, concerns regarding the operational practices of these entities are reportedly known to organisations operating internationally. It is further suggested that these NGOs played a significant role in complicating returnee's cases, potentially contributing to stigmatisation.

Plate 4: Group Photo of Some Participants at the Stakeholders' Expert Panel at Abuja, Nigeria, in 2023. Courtesy: Ngozi Uzomah (2023).

In Nigeria, stigmatisation is a significant barrier for many returnees. In various regions, there is a prevailing belief that individuals who travel abroad should return with material wealth, such as houses and cars. When returnees do not meet these expectations, they may view their migration experiences as failures, and leading to increased vulnerability and reluctance to return to their communities. This stigma can result in returnees opting to settle in other areas where they feel less pressure and can rebuild their lives without facing judgment from their peers. Providing them with reintegration support, no matter how modest, can help them cope emotionally and psychologically before re-engaging with their home communities. The vulnerability of returnees and the need for psychological and emotional support are expressed in a stakeholders' expert forum by a participant from the WOTCLEF:

“The assessment of reintegration challenges begins with profiling and counselling returnees. This initial step is vital for understanding the specific issues they face and identifying vulnerabilities that may hinder their successful reintegration. Vulnerabilities can vary widely and may include lack of adequate shelter which can significantly affect a returnee's stability; employment opportunities because many returnees struggle to find jobs. This is critical for their financial independence and access to finance including difficulties in securing financial resources thereby

impeding their ability to start businesses or support themselves. Other challenges are access to public services as navigating bureaucratic processes to obtain essential services can be overwhelming. Additionally, women may experience unique vulnerabilities, particularly if they have faced trauma during their migration journey, such as trafficking. Identifying these vulnerabilities is essential for tailoring support programmes to meet the specific needs of returnees.”

While some cultural practices in Nigeria facilitate the reintegration of returnees, with many communities having traditional rites and ceremonies to welcome back individuals and ease their transition, this positive cultural aspect is often undermined. Furthermore, returnees are typically not returned to their home communities or airports close to them, but rather to major cities like Lagos, Abuja, and Kano, effectively severing this vital cultural connection and hindering reintegration. This issue was highlighted by a staff member of a government agency during the stakeholders’ expert panel:

“The migrants should not be returned to these big cities only. Do you know that in various regions of Nigeria, there are cultural and traditional ways of welcoming, accepting and reinserting deviants in the society? Returnees are perceived as deviants and are supposed to be reintegrated in the same manner into their various communities. Don’t think that what happens in the Northern Nigeria or Middle-Belt of Nigeria can work in the western or eastern part of Nigeria. They all have their distinct cultures including in welcoming returnees. So, rather than returning them in Lagos, Abuja and Kano where they are still perceived as migrant strangers, it will be better to return them to airports closer to their origin communities which they have cultural affinities and affective with”.

This quote underscores the vital need for culturally sensitive strategies in migrant reintegration in Nigeria, arguing against a “one-size-fits-all” approach, particularly for major cities. It emphasises aligning reintegration efforts with the distinct cultural practices of each region and advocates for a community-based approach. However, community and traditional leaders, whose perspectives and expertise are crucial for incorporating these community views into decision-making, are notably absent from the migration governance framework and the NMD. Similarly, while the Ministry of Education and the National Universities Commission are represented within the NCC, academic participation in return and reintegration policy has been historically limited due to the lack of emphasis on migration within the educational system. Consequently, policy formulation, evaluation, and discussions on emerging migration issues have largely relied on the contributions of individual academics, whose inputs are rare within the broader migration governance framework as pointed out by stakeholders in a TWG meeting. Ultimately, without adequate post-return reintegration support that is culturally sensitive and community-based, a substantial portion of returnees seek to re-migrate. Moreover, due to the close communication networks between communities in origin and destination countries, negative return experiences can discourage other irregularised migrants in Europe from returning, as this information is disseminated (Wampuk, 2019).

5.2 Challenges in Cooperation on Returns

The dynamics of international cooperation on return governance are characterised by hegemonic relationships. The power asymmetry between the EU and Nigeria is evident, particularly in trade and migration policies. As a result, EU policies tend to dominate the discourse, and Nigerian stakeholders often find themselves navigating this unequal landscape primarily due to personal or special interests. Without financial backing from Europe, many officials rely on sponsorship for scholarships, workshops, and training, which creates a dependency that complicates governance. Additionally, many Nigerian political leaders recognise that the economic challenges and political instability in Nigeria are often exacerbated by Western countries. This awareness leads to ineffective migration management and hesitance in cooperating with the EU on readmission agreements, since they perceive these agreements as potentially detrimental to Nigeria's interests. Organisations like IOM, ICMPD, and GIZ engage in the Nigerian migration scene largely due to the government's inability to manage migration effectively. However, some Nigerians are apprehensive of these organisations. At the NMD event, some CSOs ask, "Why do the EU hide themselves, why are they not mentioning EU here but only IOM?"

The cooperation between Nigeria and the EU and its member states has not proven efficient or successful in facilitating returns. Contributing factors include poor governance and a lack of prioritisation in addressing migration issues. Many returns are characterised as coerced rather than voluntary (Caselli & Marcu, 2024), rendering them illegal and undermining the dignity of returnees. There is no comprehensive dialogue to address these issues, and the current legal frameworks are insufficient. The National Migration Policy of 2015 and other policy documents are filled with gaps that need urgent attention, and the government agencies have low capacity to manage migration governance in the country. This normally pave way for international organisations to come in. Under the Refugee Convention, states are responsible for the welfare of migrants, including returnees, but where this is not feasible, institutions like IOM, ICMPD, and GIZ are expected to step in. The activities of these institutions which facilitate quarterly meetings, NMD, policy development, and reviews, sponsored by the EU and its member states, create a circle of dependency and hegemony in the RRR landscape in the country. This circle is perpetuated as external actors define the parameters of assistance and influence policy direction, effectively controlling the solutions to Nigeria's migration challenges, thereby undermining its sovereignty in migration governance. This reliance on external funding also contributes to a situation where stakeholders, initially resistant to RRR initiatives, are now engaging primarily due to perceived relevance and potential economic gains. Therefore, these strategies, whether intentionally or not, align with aspects of biopolitical and disciplinary rationality (Ahouga, 2024), which contribute to the increased involvement of Nigerian migration stakeholders in RRR and the country's reliance on external funding. Despite the potential benefits of these funds, significant concerns remain. The concerns centre on the risk of corruption and the potential for violations of migrants' fundamental human rights and international legal frameworks. Such apprehensions are particularly acute as some of the funding for these initiatives originates from flexible financial instruments that lack rigorous scrutiny and oversight, increasing the risk of misuse and a lack of proper accountability. This cycle of dependency and external funding not only compromises Nigeria's ability to independently manage its migration affairs but also that of cross-border mobility in the Economic for West African States (ECOWAS). Ignoring national and regional contexts in donor-driven policies harms regional security, social cohesion, and cross-border

movement (Jegen, 2019). The dependency has created a system where external actors wield considerable influence over policy direction and implementation, potentially prioritising their own agendas over the genuine needs of Nigerian returnees.

Furthermore, Nigeria's reluctance to cooperate with signing official readmission agreements is often tied to concerns over remittances, highlighting the need for the government to articulate its own interests more clearly. Remittances from migrants play a crucial role in Nigeria's economy, creating a reluctance to formalise readmission agreements that could jeopardise this flow of income. This is captured in an interview with a stakeholder in the field:

“The most dominance benefit is in different aspects, (both) for the European and the Nigerian government and for migrants. For the European governments, they try to control their borders and make sure they have a national security; for the Nigerian [government], they know migrants can bring back money to support their families back home; and somehow for the migrant, they are interested in the reintegration package and stability. [Afterall], the European(s) [governments] do not want migrants to come to their place [Europe]”.

Nigeria engages in various forms of collaboration on migration-related issues with several countries and regional bodies. Formally, this cooperation is manifested through signed MOUs and partnerships. For instance, a 2010 agreement with Switzerland outlines cooperation in areas such as developing immigration administration capabilities, linking migration with development, protecting human rights, combating smuggling and trafficking, aiding return and reintegration, and preventing irregular migration (The Federal Council, 2010). Furthermore, platforms like the Common Agendas on Migration and Mobility, the Migration Partnership Facility, and the Rabat Process have facilitated cooperation between Nigeria and the EU, along with its member states, focusing on labour mobility and legal migration (Frasca, 2023; ICMPD, 2022b). Nigeria is also actively working on or revising comparable formal agreements with individual European nations, specifically Austria, Belgium, Germany, the Netherlands, Italy, Malta, and Spain, with a particular emphasis on the return of Nigerians with irregular status.

In addition to these arrangements, Nigeria also maintains informal agreements and MOUs with the EU and its member states. These include practical cooperation arrangements with the IOM for return operations, and various non-legally binding MOUs centered on migration management and information sharing. These informal arrangements have been notably facilitated by the EU's increasing focus on operational returns and development initiatives. However, Nigeria's engagement with North African governments presents a different picture. While cooperation exists in areas like trade and infrastructure, there are currently no formal agreements on the return and readmission of Nigerian migrants. This stance by North African countries reflects their broader foreign policy objectives and their efforts to maintain positive relations with other African nations (Lahlou & Belhaj, 2025).

The absence of formal return and readmission agreements with both the EU and North African countries have some consequences. This lack of a structured framework has resulted in a disorganised and ad-hoc return process, severely impacting the capacity to effectively reintegrate Nigerian returnees. This often leads to undignified returns and the problematic

practice of returning migrants to countries other than their origins, further complicating their reintegration and diminishing their life experiences. Moreover, poor planning and coordination by the Nigerian government in managing these returns contribute to economic strain, exacerbating existing unemployment and insecurity within the country. Despite these considerable challenges and the lack of robust formal agreements, Nigerian migrants continue to be returned in significant numbers, as host countries maintain the sovereign authority under international law to determine who can remain within their borders and who must leave.

Finally, the German government's approach, distinct from formal agreements, involves its development agency GIZ, which has a substantial presence and allocates significant resources in Nigeria, including for return and reintegration. However, allegations persist regarding informal compensatory arrangements benefiting Nigerian government officials through GIZ. This covert system may explain the perceived lack of responsiveness to anti-deportation protests and the continued deportations from Germany, and this informal model appears to be gaining traction with other European nations like Denmark and the Netherlands, potentially indicating a shift towards less transparent return management practices.

6. Conclusion

This research reveals that Nigeria's Return Migration Infrastructure (RMI), despite its broad framework of actors and policies, faces significant systemic challenges that undermine its effectiveness. Data inconsistencies, coordination gaps, corruption, and funding limitations create inefficiencies and hinder successful reintegration outcomes. The prioritisation of funder compliance over the genuine needs of returnees, as evidenced through stakeholder interviews, leads to operational shortcomings and inequities, undermining the RMI's intended impact.

Specific weaknesses are evident across the stages of return. Pre-departure processes are hampered by inadequate civil registration and documentation complexities. The arrival stage is marked by disparities in treatment and stigmatisation based on returnee classifications. The reintegration phase is particularly problematic, suffering from skill mismatches, insufficient psychosocial support, and societal stigma. Compounding these issues are IOM vendor preferential treatment and forced reintegration programmes that disregard returnee preferences. Moreover, the practice of not returning individuals to their home communities significantly hinders cultural reintegration. Monitoring and evaluation efforts are undermined by operational deficiencies and a lack of genuine capacity-building.

Furthermore, the research exposes problematic dynamics in international cooperation, particularly with the EU. Hegemonic relationships influence Nigeria's migration governance, often prioritising external interests. The absence of formal readmission agreements contributes to ad-hoc, undignified returns, creating a dependency on international organisations. Alarming cases of human rights violations against deportees, including mistreatment, abandonment and inadequate consular support, underscore the urgent need for robust protection mechanisms. The profound human cost of these systemic failures is illustrated by the distressing experiences of deportees, including cases of abusive treatment and deportation of sick migrants and minors. These instances, marked by severe trauma, lack of adequate consular intervention, and significant reintegration challenges, highlight the

profound and multifaceted trauma inflicted by forced deportation and the immense difficulties in reintegration. The detrimental impact of stigmatisation within Nigerian communities further hinders reintegration efforts.

The NCFRMI Act 2022 establishes a governance framework designed to enhance collaboration and communication aiming to manage migration, including returns, for the safety and well-being of migrants. However, this framework is significantly influenced by the EU, which often frames migration primarily as a problem, raising concerns about its effectiveness for Nigerian returnees and potentially contributing to corruption. Similarly, while the NMD offers a crucial platform for multi-stakeholder engagement on migration, including return and reintegration, it largely excludes traditional and community leaders, town unions, and traditional chiefs, with only limited religious leader participation. This absence creates a significant disconnect between policy discussions and the grassroots realities and reintegration contexts of returnees. Consequently, despite the NMD's efforts to address specific challenges, the RMI continues to grapple with systemic issues, exacerbated by the framework's inadequacy and the limited community-level input.

This research offers significant contributions to migration literature by challenging linear reintegration models and providing empirical evidence for the theoretical claims regarding power dynamics in migration governance. It reveals the complex, non-linear reality of return, marked by setbacks and trauma, advocating for dynamic, context-specific frameworks. Moreover, it underscores how external actors, particularly the EU, shape Nigeria's RMI, often prioritising external agendas over returnee needs. Finally, the findings highlight a complex and challenged RMI in Nigeria, characterised by data inconsistencies, coordination gaps, external influences, human rights concerns, and reintegration difficulties. These issues, poignantly illustrated by the distressing experiences of deportees, necessitate a re-evaluation of current practices to ensure the RMI effectively serves Nigerian returnees, even as the NMD provides a vital space for ongoing discussion and potential reform.

7. Recommendations

To address the significant challenges in identifying Nigerian migrants abroad, a dedicated institution should be established within Nigeria. This institution would expedite the provision of identification documents by leveraging existing identification numbers like the Bank Verification Number and National Identification Number and creating a dedicated assistance hotline and fostering collaboration among law enforcement and financial entities. Furthermore, stakeholders from international organisations advocate for streamlined passport issuance and replacement procedures while others believe it will lead to rights violations.

Given that current return pathways often exacerbate stigma and fail to leverage the skills acquired by migrants, European countries should explore alternative, multilateral return pathways. These pathways should include skill training and potential resettlement in third countries, recognising the value of returnees' expertise. Improved agreements among African nations would facilitate these pathways and mitigating stigma and risks. Furthermore, considering the documented instances where reintegration programmes have proven

ineffective, and funds have been misappropriated, long-term integration programmes within Europe should be explored as a viable alternative for suitable cases.

To address economic instability and inadequate regional cooperation, which hinder effective reintegration, trade, income, and tax policies should be systematically improved to enhance economic attractiveness in African countries. Aligning with Adam Smith's assertion that Africa should focus on adding value to its natural resources, robust economic foundations must be established as shared in a stakeholders meeting. Bilateral agreements among West African nations should be developed to foster cooperative migration strategies, and the inadequacies of current regional migration protocols, including the 90-day stay under ECOWAS agreements, should be addressed. Initiatives like visa-free travel and enhanced intra-regional migration quality should be promoted. All these will encourage Nigerians to migrate to African countries rather than to Europe where they are not welcomed.

Since CSOs play a vital role in addressing gaps in reintegration support, but their efforts are often hampered by lack of coordination and funding, NCFRMI should actively engage with CSOs and other stakeholders to enhance the effectiveness of reintegration programs, moving beyond reliance on external consultants. The government should demonstrate political will by funding the structures established by CSOs and create a coordinated approach to minimise redundancy and maximise impact.

As the community is the context of returnee reintegration, establishing regionally representative advisory councils within the NMD and governance framework to effectively involve community and traditional leaders is necessary to ensure their direct participation and input in policy and reintegration efforts.

To ensure an efficient RMI and address the research-demonstrated mismatch between acquired skills and local opportunities, prioritising agricultural skills training within Nigeria is crucial. Furthermore, as corruption poses a major challenge to Nigeria's RMI, strengthening governance is imperative. This entails enthroning transparency, ensuring programme integrity through fair vendor selection, demanding accountability on activities of FRONTEx, implementing rigorous audits, establishing clear reporting systems, harmonising efforts across agencies, ensuring adequate funding, prioritising returnee needs, and fostering ethical conduct among officials. By addressing both the skill-opportunity mismatch and corruption, Nigeria can mitigate its impact, improve RMI efficiency, and uphold migrants' right.

Considering the deficiencies in capacity building and support systems as demonstrated in the Migrant Transit Centre and other entities, resulting in inadequate assistance for returnees, comprehensive training and resources for all actors involved in reintegration should be provided. Robust referral networks should be established to address the psychosocial needs of returnees, and an economic reintegration support system should be developed to provide financial assistance and information about available resources to facilitate a smoother transition.

To address the hegemonic relationships and power asymmetries between Europe and Nigeria, which negatively impact relationships and returnees, transparent and equitable dialogues should be initiated. These dialogues should aim to establish mutually beneficial agreements

that respect the sovereignty and interests of Nigeria. Mechanisms should be put in place to ensure accountability and prevent the exploitation of power imbalances, fostering a more balanced and respectful partnership. Critically, these dialogues and mechanisms must also address the ways in which hegemonic relationships reinforce corruption, ensuring that financial and operational transparency is prioritised and that resources are allocated in a manner that directly benefits returnees and strengthens Nigerian institutions. This includes a shift towards collaborative, co-designed programmes that prioritise the needs of Nigerian returnees.

Finally, to mitigate the defensiveness and distrust observed among international organisations, CSOs, government agencies, researchers, academia, and other stakeholders, regular and structured platforms for dialogue and information sharing should be established. These platforms should foster transparency, accountability, and mutual respect, encouraging open communication and collaboration. Joint research initiatives, workshops, and conferences should be organised to facilitate knowledge exchange and build trust. Independent oversight mechanisms should be implemented to ensure that all stakeholders adhere to ethical standards and best practices, promoting a more collaborative and effective approach to return and reintegration.

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